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Organisation responsible Radboud University

Tasks and responsibilities in research data management at Radboud University

This document specifies the research data management (RDM) responsibilities associated with each role. For certain positions, only RDM-related tasks are included, while other responsibilities are beyond the scope of this document.

1. Executive Board

The executive board is ultimately responsible for good research data management. The executive board is also responsible for:

- ensuring (access to) adequate central infrastructure and support at the central level to meet the requirements of Radboud University's RDM policy
- determining Radboud University's RDM policy and frameworks

2. Legal affairs

Legal affairs is responsible for:

- providing guidance on the compliance of RDM policies and infrastructure with legal requirements
- providing guidance on data and software licensing, copyright, and data use agreements

3. Academic Affairs

Academic Affairs is responsible for advising on and developing RDM policy and strategy in research and education

4. Information & Library Services (ILS)

ILS is responsible for providing (access to) infrastructure and support to facilitate responsible data management. This includes:

- A dedicated tool for data management planning
- Systems and support for the storage, backup, and safe sharing of research data during research
- A registration tool for research data
- A data repository and support for the long-term preservation and FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) publication of research data

4.1 Digital Competence Centre (DCC)

The digital competence centre is responsible for:

- Main contributor to the developments of RDM policies (general Radboud University policy and institutional RDM policies)
- Creating a vision and approach for RDM support
- Functioning as a central knowledge hub on good RDM
- Creating a vision for and coordinating the data repository and data management plan tool
- Providing support and training on RDM for data stewards
- Providing training and online information on RDM for researchers

4.2 Privacy organization

The privacy organization is responsible for advising on RDM policies and infrastructure to comply with privacy regulations

5. Within faculties

5.1 Deans

The dean is responsible for:

- implementation of RDM in the bachelor and master curricula
- ensuring that sufficient support and infrastructure is available within education and research institutes to allow compliance with the RDM policies of Radboud University and the institute, funding agencies, and scientific journals

5.2 Director of research

The director of research is responsible for:

- the development, establishment, and possible modification of the research institute's RDM policy, and for ensuring its implementation and compliance
- supervising compliance to the RDM policies by research institutes
- ensuring that a qualified individual evaluates the necessity of continued preservation after the dataset's minimum preservation period

5.3 Researchers

- Along with the project manager, the researcher is primarily responsible for the effective management of research data, and consequently adherence to the policy of the research institute and (if applicable) the external funder
- The researcher is responsible for being aware of and complying with relevant regulations regarding personal data (e.g., GDPR) and ethics
- The researcher is responsible for budgeting for the costs of RDM in research projects

5.3.1 PhD candidates

In addition to those responsibilities of the researcher, the PhD candidate is also responsible for adhering to the doctorate regulations

5.4 Director of education

The director of education is responsible for enforcing Radboud University's RDM policy, insofar as it relates to academic higher education, and ensuring that students are informed

5.5 Students

The student is responsible for adhering to Radboud University's RDM policy as it applies to education

5.6 Privacy officers

The privacy officer of the faculty is responsible for informing researchers about relevant developments and guidelines regarding personal data and supporting them in adhering to them

5.7 Ethics committees

The ethics committees are responsible for alignment of ethical procedures with the relevant RDM policies

5.8 Data Stewards

The data steward is responsible for:

- Providing first line RDM support to researchers by:
 - Informing researchers about RDM policies and infrastructure specific to their research discipline and institute
 - Ensuring that data management plans receive adequate feedback
 - Answering RDM related questions from researchers
 - Familiarizing themselves with the ethical and legal issues that relate to the research data within their own discipline, and referring researchers to the relevant advisors and committees in this field
 - Assisting in compliance with the research institute's RDM policy
- Actively contributing to the implementation and updating of the research institute's RDM policy
- Advising the director of research on the implementation of and compliance with the institute's RDM policy
- Encouraging FAIR and open science practices among researchers

- Staying abreast of new developments in RDM by taking part in the activities and initiatives facilitated by the DCC. Additionally, accruing discipline-specific knowledge needed to answer researchers' questions